

SOLIDIFICATION MECHANISM IN THE SQUEEZE CASTING OF
METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effects of different fibers and matrices on the solidification behavior of metal matrix composites have been investigated during squeeze casting with and without the remelting. Three different fibers - Boron and two kinds of SiC - which have different chemical compositions and diameters are used for the reinforcement and Al-4.5wt%Cu and Al-10wt%Mg alloys for the matrices. The regularity of the primary α phase and the non-equilibrium eutectic distribution around the fibers is investigated to find whether the fibers serve as the heterogeneous nucleation site during the solidification. The average secondary dendrite arm spacing in the reinforced alloy and in the unreinforced alloy is also measured to know the role of the fibers during the solidification. The relations between the microsegregation and the cooling rate, the reinforcements and the matrices are also observed to determine specific influential process parameters in actual squeeze casting process.

KEY WORDS: Squeeze Casting; Matrix, Aluminum; Heterogeneous Nucleation; Solidification ; Microsegregation

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composite(MMC)s which have not only high specific strength and stiffness but also better thermo and electromechanical properties than polymer matrix composites have been applied to the high performance required engineering fields such as space, automobile and electropackaging fields even though the speed is slow but steady[1-2]. Among several processings, liquid phase processing of MMCs has been considered as very economical way to produce MMCs. Squeeze casting among several liquid phase processings has been considered and applied to fabricate MMCs because of its several advantages such as obtaining

the fine microstructure of the matrix and increasing wettability between the fiber/matrix region by the applied pressure. Additionally, this method is very appropriate to produce near-net shape MMCs on a large scale and can be worked practically by the modification of available die-casting equipment[3-5]. There are very few papers available for the solidification behavior of MMCs in squeeze casting of MMCs compared with the works done for the optimization of the manufacturing process and the characterization of the fiber/matrix interfaces[6]. However, the understanding of the solidification behavior during the processing is basically required to suggest the guideline of the processing conditions. Especially, the role of the fiber in the solidification of MMC processing should be clearly discussed for the further argument. At present, there are two distinguished arguments. One is the idea of Cornie and Levi which reported that the fiber does not play a role as the heterogeneous nucleation site in the processing of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-Cu}$ MMCs through the observation of the non-equilibrium eutectic at the fiber/matrix region[7-11]. The other is the idea of Fukunaga and Abe which observed the opposite results in the processing of $\text{SiC}/\text{Al-Cu}$ and TiC/Al MMCs[12-14].

The aim of this paper is therefore to clarify the role of the fiber during the squeeze casting of MMCs with different fibers and matrices under different processing conditions. Boron and SiC continuous fibers are chosen as the reinforcement fibers and Al-4.5wt%Cu and Al-10wt%Mg are for the matrices. The effects of the fiber on the subsequent solidification microstructures and the solute microsegregation in the reinforced region and in the unreinforced region are investigated with respect to the fibers and the cooling rate. Also, the effect of the temperature difference between the fiber and the matrix melted on the secondary dendrite arm spacing is observed with as-squeeze cast specimens and the remelting and resolidified specimens.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Fabrication of MMC Specimens Reinforcement fibers used in this study are AVCO's 100 μm diameter continuous Boron fiber, 140 μm diameter SiC(SCS-2) fiber, and Nippon Carbon's 15 μm diameter Nicalon SiC fiber. Matrices of Al-4.5wt%Cu, Al-10wt%Mg, and Al-4.5wt%Cu-0.7wt%Ti are chosen and prepared by using an induction furnace. With these constituent materials, MMC specimens are produced by using a squeeze casting equipment as shown in Figure 1 and by following the fabrication step as shown in Figure 2. MMC Specimens produced for this study are summarized and designated in Table 1. The preforms of 140 μm diameter Boron and SiC fibers are prepared by tying each ends. Nicalon fibers which are small diameters and flexible can be placed in a special preform jig to make uniform arrangement. Preforms prepared are clean in acetone and heated up to 320 °C in the mold. The matrix metals are overheated to 800 °C and poured into the preform of the mold. Then, the pressure is applied after 7 seconds delay time for 90 seconds duration time. During applying the pressure, the mold is cooled down in the cooling rate 20~40 K/min by varying the pressure of liquid nitrogen gas. The applied pressure is 40 MPa for Boron and SCS-2 fiber reinforced

Figure 1. Schematic drawing of a squeeze casting equipment

Figure 2. Squeeze casting process step of MMCs

	Fiber	Matrix	Mold Temp. (°C)	Furnace Temp. (°C)	Cooling Rate (°C/min)
BA-1	Boron	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	20
BA-2	Boron	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	32
BA-3	Boron	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	39
BB-1	Boron	Al-10%Mg	500	800	32
KA-1	SCS-2	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	20
KA-2	SCS-2	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	32
KA-3	SCS-2	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	39
KB-1	SCS-2	Al-10%Mg	500	800	32
KC-1	SCS-2	Al-4.5%Cu- 0.7%Ti	500	800	32
SA-1	Nicalon	Al-4.5%Cu	500	800	32
SB-1	Nicalon	Al-10%Mg	500	800	32

Table 1. Designations and chemical compositions of MMC specimens

MMC specimens and 75 MPa for Nicalon fiber reinforced MMC specimens on the basis of Kelvin and Blake-Kozeny equations[15].

2.2 Remelting and Heat Treatment In order to observe the solidification behavior in the non-temperature gradient between the fiber and the matrix, as-squeeze cast specimens are remelted over 650 °C and slowly cooled to 530 °C and finally quenched. Also, to observe the effect of the homogenization time on the microsegregation in the fiber/matrix region, Al-4.5wt%Cu MMCs are homogenized at 530 °C and Al-10wt%Mg MMCs are at 430 °C. Prepared as-

squeeze cast and remelted specimens both are sectioned by a slow diamond cutter and polished with diamond paste. Etching to delineate the solidification microstructure is with the usual 10% NaOH solution or Keller reagent.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Solidification Microstructure Solidification microstructures of the reinforced region and the unreinforced region in 140 μm diameter SCS-2 SiC fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu MMCs are compared. Figure 3 (a) shows the solidification microstructure of as-squeeze cast (preform temperature 320 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and matrix temperature 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) MMC specimen. Figure 3 (b) shows the solidification microstructure of remelted at 650 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and resolidified MMC specimen. It is noticed in Figure 3(a) that the secondary dendrite arm spacing (DAS) of the reinforced region in as-squeeze cast MMC is about 10 μm in average which is significantly smaller than about 27 μm of the unreinforced region. However, the DAS of each regions in the remelted and resolidified MMC is increased to 40 μm and 50 μm . Thus, the DAS of the reinforced and unreinforced region is almost same in the non-temperature gradient between the fiber and the matrix.

Figure 3. (a) As-squeeze cast SCS-2 SiC/Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC (b) Remelted SCS-2 SiC/Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC

Figure 4 shows the solidification microstructure of as-squeeze cast SCS-2 SiC/Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC. The primary α phase and non-equilibrium θ phase (Al_2Cu) both are found. Figure 5 shows the solidification microstructure of as-squeeze cast B/Al-10wt%Mg MMC. There are primary α phase and non-equilibrium β phase (Al_3Mg_2 , Al_8Mg_5) in this MMC. No matter what reinforcement fibers and matrix metals, non-equilibrium eutectic are found irregularly around the fiber/matrix interfaces in as-squeeze cast MMCs. The variation of the DAS in different constituent materials of MMCs is summarized in Table 2. The DAS of 140 μm diameter SCS-2 fiber reinforced MMC is little bit smaller than 100 μm diameter Boron fiber reinforced MMC. In different matrix metals of Al-10wt%Mg and Al-4.5wt%Cu, the DAS of Al-10wt%Mg is larger than the other.

Figure 4. As-squeeze cast SCS-2
SiC/Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC

Figure 5. As-squeeze cast
B/Al-10wt%Mg MMC

Sample	Reinforced region (μ)	Unreinforced region (μ)	Interfiber spacing (μ)
KA-2	9.8	26.9	32.8
BA-2	11.5	26.9	31.4
KB-1	15.8	34.2	32.8
BB-1	16.9	34.2	31.4
KC-1	8.9	24.5	32.8

Table 2. Secondary dendrite arm spacing of MMC specimens

Figure 6 shows the microstructure of as-squeeze cast Nicalon fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC. The solidification microstructure of this small diameter fiber reinforced MMC is very much similar to those of Boron and SCS-2 fiber reinforced MMCs. However, the DAS of this MMC is decreased to about $4 \mu\text{m}$ because of its intrinsic smaller interfiber spacing (IFS). Figure 7 shows the result of line profiling around the fiber/matrix interfaces of SCS-2 SiC fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC. It is known that the Cu content (white portion) which is irregularly distributed around the interface is measured about 32-34%. Figure 8 shows the solidification microstructures of SCS-2 SiC fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu (a) and Al-10wt%Mg (b) which remelted at 650°C and resolidified to 530°C and 430°C slowly and quenched. Apart from as-squeeze cast MMCs, non-equilibrium eutectics and the solute content are exist and enriched regularly around the interfaces.

3.2 Microsegregation The microsegregation with respect to the matrix metal is investigated by energy dispersive spectrometer for squeeze cast SCS-2 fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC and Al-10wt%Mg MMC. Figure 9 shows that the microsegregation in Al-10wt%Mg MMC is lower than in Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC.

Figure 6. Microstructure of as-squeeze cast Nicalon fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC

Figure 7. Line profiling of SCS-2 SiC/Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Remelted solidification microstructures of SCS-2 SiC fiber reinforced (a) Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC (b) Al-10wt%Mg MMC

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. EDS of SCS-2 SiC reinforced (a) Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC (b) Al-10wt%Mg MMC

In Table 3, the ratio of the maximum and the minimum of the solute concentration $S(\max/\min)$ for the Cu and Mg in different specimens are denoted. The solute concentration is measured in the small triangle interstice of the fibers which is about 50 μm . It is found in Table 3 that the value of S in small diameter fiber reinforced MMC and in Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC is lower than in large diameter fiber Boron or SCS-2 fiber reinforced MMC and in Al-10wt%Mg MMC. Thus, the microsegregation is decreased in the smaller diameter fiber reinforced Al-4.5wt%Cu MMCs. The effects of the cooling rate and the fiber on the microsegregation is shown in Figure 10 for Al-4.5wt%Cu MMCs with respect to the S of Cu in the alloy. Here, the microsegregation is increased with respect to the increasing cooling rate. This is similarly found in Al-10wt%Mg MMCs.

Composites S	BA-2	BB-1	KA-2	KB-1	KC-1	SA-1	SB-1
Ratio of Max./Min. Conc.	8.43	1.93	8.24	2.15	9.64	7.07	1.53

Table 3. Microsegregation of squeeze cast MMCs

Figure 10. The variation of Cu concentration with respect to the cooling rate

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Nucleation Sites in MMCs Levi[11] reported that the Cu concentration of CuAl_2O_4 , $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, and CuAl_2 was uniformly found at the fiber/matrix interface by the chemical reaction of the fiber and the liquid phase matrix metal when Al_2O_3 fiber was heated up to 1270 K to produce MMCs with Al-4.5wt%Cu by compocasting. In the other aspect, Cornie[7-10] reported that the minimum Cu concentration was found in the matrix region surrounded by the fibers and the non-equilibrium eutectic of the final solidification microstructure was found at the fiber/matrix interface when $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al-4.5wt}\% \text{Cu}$ MMCs, which produced by pressure

infiltration, were remelted at over liquidus temperature 650 °C and resolidified. Also, the dendrite arm spacing in the reinforced region and in the unreinforced region of the MMC was not significantly changed. In this study, with the remelted and resolidified as-squeeze cast MMCs, very similar things are occurred; the non-equilibrium eutectic of the final solidification microstructure is exist regularly at the fiber/matrix interface. the dendrite arm spacing is not changed considerably between the reinforced region and the unreinforced region. These observations may draw that the fiber is not considered as the heterogeneous nucleation catalyst during the solidification of MMC when the temperature gradient is not exist between the constituent materials. However, Fukunaga[13-14] reported that the non-equilibrium eutectic was irregularly happened around the fibers due to the applied pressure when SiC fibers which preheated at 550 °C was impregnated by Al-4.5wt%Cu which melted to 700 °C during the squeeze casting. Also, Abe[12] reported TiC act as heterogeneous nucleation catalysts (grain refiner) in Al. In this study, with MMCs which produced under the condition of 500 °C difference between the fiber and the matrix during the squeeze casting, it is found similar to the observations of Fukunaga that the non-equilibrium eutectic is irregularly found in the interface region. In addition to this observation, the DAS in the reinforced region and in the unreinforced region is compared for their size. It can be drawn that the fiber acts as the nucleation catalysts when there is significant temperature difference between the fiber and the matrix through the observation of reduced DAS in the reinforced region by the effect of the fiber. Here, the fiber which is lower temperature is considered as a role to increase the site of heterogeneous nucleation or to detach the dendrite arm during applying the pressure.

4.2 Effects of Cooling Rate and the Fiber on Microsegregation During the solidification, the maximum microsegregation of the solute caused by the different diffusion rate of the solid and the liquid can be predicted by Scheil equations. The minimum microsegregation is occurred when the solidification is very close to the equilibrium solidification. However, if the solid state diffusion is considered, the microsegregation can be predicted by the following equation;

$$C_s = k C_0 \left[1 - \frac{f_s}{1 + (D_s \cdot 4t_f / d^2)} \right]^{k-1}$$

Here, the critical variable $M(=4t_f/d^2)$ in the denominator is increasing with the decreasing DAS d when the solidification time is constant, which consequently reducing the microsegregation. By employing this relation for this study, the observation of the less microsegregation in the reinforced region of as-squeeze cast MMCs than in the unreinforced region is explained by that the reduced DAS in the reinforced region by the heterogeneous nucleation at the fibers brings the increasing solid state diffusion because of reduced diffusion distance. Especially, the solid state diffusion may affect remarkably the microsegregation in the small interstice of the small diameter fiber reinforced MMC. The microsegregation is reduced as decreasing cooling rate in the final stage of the solidification - 15 seconds after applying the pressure in this study. This is understood as the increasing diffusion time for the back diffusion of the solute in the solid. The microsegregation is also reduced in Nicalon fiber reinforced MMC (IFS 5.6 μ m) than in Boron

fiber reinforced MMC(IFS 31.4 μ m) and in SCS-2 fiber reinforced MMC(IFS 32.8 μ m). It is supposed that the distance of the diffusion is restricted by the geometrical arrangement of the small diameter fibers. Also, the reasons of less microsegregation in Al-10wt%Mg MMC than in Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC may be found that the partition coefficient k of Al-10wt%Mg($k=0.5$) is bigger than that of Al-4.5wt%Cu($k=0.2$) and the diffusion coefficient D_s of Mg in aluminum is larger than that of Cu in aluminum.

4. CONCLUSION

1. The fibers act as heterogeneous nucleation catalysts during the squeeze casting of MMCs when the temperature gradient is significantly large between the fiber and the pouring matrix melt. However, the role of the fibers for the heterogeneous nucleation is not considered as the same as the above statement when MMCs squeeze cast are remelted and resolidified to simulate non-temperature gradient between the fiber and the matrix. These two opposite statements are explained by observing the lessening dendrite arm spacing in the reinforced region, and the primary α and the non-equilibrium eutectic irregularly at the fiber/matrix interface.

2. The microsegregation in the matrix alloy is decreased with the decreasing cooling rate and with the small diameter of the fiber in MMCs. The effect of the matrix on the microsegregation is more severe in Al-10wt%Mg MMC than in Al-4.5wt%Cu MMC. These are supposed to be explained with different partition coefficient k and diffusion coefficient D_s .

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